

Pre-registration: Aging Study UMR_SNC_045

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Motivation:

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have achieved remarkable progress in power conversion efficiency, making them one of the most promising emerging photovoltaic technologies. Despite these advances, long-term stability and reproducibility remain critical challenges for commercialization.

In typical experimental practice, multiple devices are fabricated within a single batch under identical processing conditions. While the overall device performance of a batch is often characterized collectively, stability and aging results are frequently reported only for one selected device. Because aging behaviour can vary significantly from device to device, reporting a single device may not fully represent the stability characteristics of the entire batch. Furthermore, without pre-registration the selection process of which devices are selected for stability tests and which stability data is going to be published is not transparent and therefore may be subjected to publication bias.

The present study is pre-registered to ensure transparency and consistency in reporting stability data. All devices fabricated within a batch will be characterized individually for both initial performance and aging behaviour. Aging curves and stability metrics will be reported for the complete number of fabricated devices rather than for a selected champion device. This approach enables evaluation of device-to-device variability in stability and allows assessment of whether conclusions drawn from single-device reporting are representative of batch-level behaviour.

Research Questions:

1. What is the distribution of initial power conversion efficiencies (PCE) among all fabricated perovskite solar cells (PSCs) with identical device architecture?
2. How does the aging performance vary across all devices in one batch?
3. Are the best-performing devices representative of the overall batch performance and stability?
4. Is the highest-efficiency cell also the most stable cell?
 - 4.1. Do we generate misleading results if we report only one cell for highest efficiency and one other cell for highest stability?

Hypotheses:

1. Initial PCEs will show significant variability across devices fabricated under identical conditions.
2. Aging rates (e.g., T80, T50) will vary among devices.
3. Choosing a single solar cell for aging can lead to false conclusions
4. Reporting only one cell for highest efficiency and one other cell for highest stability can lead to false conclusions.

Study Design:

- This study is pre-registered prior to solar cell fabrication and data collection. Total number of solar cells: a total of 144 solar cells planar n-i-p perovskite solar cells (PSCs) will be fabricated for this study, divided into two device architectures:
 - **Stack A:** Glass/FTO/SnO₂/Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.85}MA_{0.10}Pb(I_{2.9} Br_{0.1})₃/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au (72 samples on 18 substrates)
 - **Stack B:** Glass/FTO/SnO₂/ Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.85}MA_{0.10}Pb(I_{2.9} Br_{0.1})₃//Carbon (72 samples on 18 substrates)
- All samples will be fabricated in one fabrication run under identical processing conditions for each deposited layer.
- External Quantum Efficiency (EQE) and current density–voltage (JV) scans to determine PCE, open circuit voltage V_{oc} , short-circuit current density J_{sc} , and fill factor FF will be measured on all devices before and after the ageing campaign.
- Ageing campaign: Aging measurements will be performed simultaneously on all samples under controlled environmental conditions in accordance with the ISOS L1 protocol, with continuous 1-sun equivalent illumination at room temperature and constant bias at the maximum power point (MPP tracking).
- Each device will be assigned a unique ID, and all raw and processed data will be stored in a structured database to ensure full traceability.
- Device for which all solar cells on a substrate have a PCE below a threshold of $PCE \leq 3\%$ can be excluded from the ageing study, since for such low performing devices we expect severe and unrepresentative failures, and all exclusions will be fully documented.

Methods

Materials

Glass/fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates were purchased from Yingkou Shangsheng Business Co. SnO₂ colloid precursor [Tin (IV) oxide, 15% in H₂O colloidal dispersion] was purchased from Solaveni. PbI₂ (99.99%, trace metals basis) was purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI). Methylammonium bromide (MABr)(99.999%, trace elements basis), formamidinium iodide (FAI)(99.999%, trace elements basis), cesium iodide (CsI)(99.99 %, trace elements basis), CEAI (2-cyclohexylethylammonium iodide), and carbon paste were purchased from Dyenamo. Dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylsulfoxid (DMSO), and isopropanol (IPA) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Ethanol ($\geq 99.8\%$) and Chlorobenzene (CB) (99.8%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Spiro-OMeTAD commercial ink (LX-MG2) was purchased from Linxole. Acetone and isopropanol for cleaning the substrates were purchased from Carl Roth.

Sample fabrication

Electron Transport Layer Deposition:

25 mm × 25 mm patterned Glass/FTO substrates will be treated in a subsequent ultrasound bath of detergent, deionized water (twice), acetone and IPA, each for 10 minutes. Subsequently, the substrates will be dried under a N₂ flow. A commercial SnO₂ colloidal dispersion in water will be prepared at a dilution ratio of 1:4 with a mixed solution of deionized water and ethanol in a ratio of 2:3. Prior to thin film deposition, the substrates will be exposed to UV-ozone treatment for 20 minutes to complete cleaning process and enhance wettability. A volume of 200 μ l of the as-prepared SnO₂ solution will be deposited onto the substrate surface via static spin coating at 5000 rpm for 30 seconds. The resulting film will subsequently be subjected to thermal annealing at 150°C for 30 minutes under ambient atmosphere.

Perovskite Absorber Deposition:

To prepare 1 ml of perovskite precursor solution with the formulation of $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.85}\text{MA}_{0.10}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{2.9}\text{Br}_{0.1})_3$, 17.91 mg of MABr, 20.78 mg of CsI, 233.88 mg of FAI, and 774.56 mg of PbI_2 will be dissolved in 1 ml of DMF:DMSO (4:1) solution in a N_2 -filled glovebox, and stirred over night at room temperature. After 20 minutes of additional UV-ozone treatment to improve the wettability of the electron transport layer (ETL), 100 μl of perovskite precursor will be deposited in the glovebox via static spin coating at 2000 rpm for 10 seconds by the acceleration 200 rpm/s and 6000 rpm for 20 seconds by the acceleration of 2000 rpm/s. 200 μl of chlorobenzene will be deposited as anti-solvent, 7 seconds before end of the second step. Subsequently, the substrates will be annealed at 100°C for 30 minutes to enhance the crystallization of the perovskite layer.

Passivation Layer:

After annealing is complete and the substrate has cooled to room temperature inside the glovebox, 80 μl of CEAI (2-cyclohexylethylammonium iodide) solution (2 mg/ml in anhydrous IPA) will be deposited onto the perovskite layer via static spin coating at 4000 rpm for 20 seconds, followed by annealing at 100°C for 10 minutes.

Hole Transport Layer Deposition:

After cooling the substrates to room temperature, 80 μl of spiro ink will be applied onto the substrate surface via static spin coating at 3000 rpm for 30 seconds in the glovebox.

Bottom Electrode Deposition:

For the metal electrode-based devices, an 80 nm gold (Au) back contact will be thermally evaporated onto the hole transport layer (HTL) at a controlled deposition rate of 0.1 nm/s under high vacuum conditions, with a base pressure maintained below 10^{-5} mbar. For the HTL-free carbon-based devices, the back electrode will be fabricated by depositing the carbon paste onto the perovskite absorber layer using the doctor-blade technique with a fixed blade gap of 200 μm . A metal mask will be employed during the deposition process to precisely define the active area of the solar cells. The carbon-based PSCs will be subsequently subjected to thermal annealing at 120°C for 15 minutes under ambient atmospheric conditions to facilitate complete solvent evaporation and ensure full solidification of the resulting carbon electrode.

Characterisation

External Quantum Efficiency (EQE):

Measurement system	Arkeo Platform CicciResearch
Measurement protocol	The chopper wheel frequency will be set to 23 Hz to enable phase-sensitive lock-in detection of the modulated photocurrent signal. The sample stage temperature will be maintained at 25°C throughout the measurement to ensure thermal stability and measurement reproducibility. Prior to sample characterization, the system will be calibrated using a reference silicon photodiode to ensure accurate spectral response determination. For the characterization of the perovskite solar cells, the wavelength range will be defined between 300 and 900 nm, encompassing the characteristic absorption spectrum of the perovskite absorber layer. All the EQE measurements will be conducted under ambient atmospheric condition.
Samples to be measured	All samples fabricated

Measurement carried out	Before and after the ageing campaign
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Current Density – Voltage (JV) measurement:

Measurement system	JV measurements: Arkeo Platform CicciResearch Solar simulator: G2V optics Sunbrick
Measurement protocol	A class AAA G2V Sunbrick LED solar simulator will be used for JV characterization of the fabricated devices. The spectral shape of the simulator output will be measured using a calibrated photo-spectrometer. The spectral shape will be adjusted via the LED-setting to be within the specifications of the AAA specification for AM1.5G and to have a low mismatch factor considering the EQE of the device under test and the EQE of a certified silicon reference solar cell. Subsequently, the overall illumination intensity will be regulated such that the certified silicon reference solar cell delivers the correct short-circuit current density under consideration of the spectral mismatch factor. The first LED settings will be based on the relative EQE measurement of the first measured sample. The settings will be re-adjusted for further samples if the mismatch factor would vary by over 2%. All devices will be measured under a shadow mask with an aperture area of 0.1 cm ² to precisely define the active area. The JV characteristics will be recorded at a scan speed of 50 mV/s in the reverse-to-forward (RV→FW) scan direction. Prior to each J-V measurement, the devices will be held at open-circuit conditions for 3 minutes to allow stabilization of the open-circuit voltage (V _{oc}) and minimize the influence of ion migration and transient effects on the measured performance parameters. All JV measurements will be conducted under ambient atmospheric conditions.
Samples to be measured	All samples fabricated
Measurement carried out	Before and after the ageing campaign

Ageing campaign:

Measurement system	MPPT: Custom made system Solar simulator: Solaronix A-45 class A solar simulator
Measurement protocol	Samples are placed in a N2 flushed air tight housing. Reference silicon photodiodes inside the housing will be used to track light intensity during ageing. The EQE and JV curves of the photodiodes will be measured before and after the ageing campaign. The light intensity is set to “1 sun”, by adjusting such that the short circuit current density (J _{sc}) measured in the aging setup matches the J _{sc} determined in the JV-measurement, making use of three perovskite solar cells with gold electrodes, with a J _{sc} determined in the JV measurement that varies by ±1% from the average J _{sc} of all samples with gold electrodes. Complementarily, the short circuit current I _{sc} of a calibrated silicon reference solar cell will be measured, the ageing campaign will be

	interrupted for a few minutes every 6 ± 1 day to re-measure the I_{sc} of this reference solar cell. All samples are measured with a photomask to define the active area of 0.1 cm^2 . Samples are in direct thermal contact with polyimide-covered aluminium blocks thermally connected to a sample holder block that is controlled to $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature of the devices will be monitored with a temperature sensor placed on one sample position inside the N2 tight housing.
Samples to be measured	All samples fabricated
Measurement carried out	Start immediately after finishing JV measurements and report the time delay between JV measurement and start of ageing. Run for at least 1,000 h or until the efficiency of the most stable device has dropped below 80% of the initial value (T80) (“Initial value”: average PCE measured over the first 60 seconds of MPPT).
Protocol for problems during the measurement campaign	If the solar simulator light intensity, monitored by photodiodes on the sample holder chuck, drops below $80\pm 5\%$, it will be re-adjusted manually. If the measurement is terminated, re-start immediately.

Analysis Plan:

For Research Question 1:

- Compute statistical distributions of initial PCE values across all devices (mean, median, standard deviation) and present results using box plots and distribution histograms for each group (gold/carbon).

For Research Questions 2 and 4:

- Plot aging curves for each individual device. Power density vs. time (absolute, not normalized values)
- Extract aging metrics such as T_{80} and T_{50} for all devices. (T_x is the time when the power has dropped to x% of the initial value)
- Compare the initial PCE of each device with its aging performance

For Research Question 3:

- Compare the “best-performing” cell with the most stable cell by plotting PCE at T_0 vs. T_{80} for each group (gold/carbon)

The solar cells will be made available after completion of the aging campaign to other researchers in the group who are investigating root causes for aging to perform further characterisation (PL based techniques, Fast-Hysteresis etc. if interest exists). The data will be available for further statistical analysis.

Appendix

Further documents, which will be uploaded to Zenodo prior to starting the aging measurements:

- csv or txt file containing efficiency and sample IDs after JV measurement
- JSON file of batch plan with processing details